

**Effects of Game-Based Learning on Students' Mathematics Achievement:
A Meta-analysis**

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How to cite this article:

Tokac U., Novak E., & Thompson C.G. (2019), Effects of game-based learning on students' mathematics achievement: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*.1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12347>

Statement on conflict of interest

We declare that there is no conflict of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this work.

Abstract

This meta-analysis investigated the effects of learning video games on mathematics achievement of PreK-12th grade students compared to traditional classroom instructional methods. Results from the 24 collected studies showed heterogeneity among effect sizes, both in magnitude and direction. Using a random-effects model, a small but marginally significant overall effect ($\bar{d}_{RE} = 0.13, p = .02$) suggested that mathematics video games contributed to higher learning gains as compared to traditional instructional methods. In addition, moderator analyses were mixed in terms of statistical significance and explored effect-size heterogeneity across effects using grade level, instrument type, length of game-based intervention, country, publication type and study year characteristics. Overall findings indicate that video games are a slightly effective instructional strategy for teaching mathematics across PreK-12th grade levels.

Keywords: *digital games, mathematics education, academic achievement, meta-analysis*

1. Introduction

Learning mathematics presents various challenges for many children due to the difficult and often tedious nature of the subject (Sedig, 2008). Educational video games have the potential to address these challenges and positively impact mathematics learning and attitudes. Video games are able to consume children's attention for hours while providing instruction and an engaging learning experience. Video games have been used to promote children's mathematics achievement in various domains including problem-solving and algebra skills (Abramovich, 2010), strategic and reasoning abilities (Bottino, Ferlino, Ott, & Tavella, 2007), critical geometry skills (Yang & Chen, 2010), and arithmetic procedures (Moreno & Duran, 2004). Nevertheless, the National Mathematics Advisory Panel (NMAP, 2008) and others (e.g., Martinez-Garza, Clark, & Nelson, 2013; Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012; Young et al., 2012) do not provide a direct recommendation for using games "as a potentially useful tool in introducing and teaching specific subject-matter content to specific populations" (NMAP, 2008; p. 51) due to the limited number of rigorous studies exploring effects of game-based learning on mathematics skills development. This meta-analysis addresses this concern by systematically examining the effects of mathematics video games used in PreK-12 curricula on student mathematics achievement compared to traditional, non-video game-based classroom instructional methods (i.e., media comparisons). In addition, we assess several possible moderating effects: *Grade Level, Instrument Type, Length of Game-Based Intervention, Country, Publication Type and Publication Year.*

In spite of the increased popularity of educational video games over the last two decades, empirical research on the effects of math video gaming on student academic achievement is inconsistent. For example, Kebritchi (2008) found that high school students

who interacted with the mathematics video game *DimensionM* outperformed their non-gaming peers. Beserra, Nussbaum, Zeni, Rodriguez, and Wurman (2014) examined third grade students' arithmetic performance in game-based and traditional classroom conditions in three different countries (Brazil, Chile, and Costa Rica). The authors found that game-based learning was more effective than a traditional classroom approach. Conversely, several studies did not show positive benefits of using video games in a mathematical classroom (e.g., Costabile, De Angeli, Roselli, Lanzilotti, & Plantamura, 2003; Gelman, 2010; Jones, 2011). For instance, Ferguson (2014) found that traditional instruction was more effective than game-based instruction for high school Algebra 1 students. Swearingen's (2011) research showed that both game-based and traditional instructional approaches were equally beneficial for teaching high school mathematics. Moreover, not only did different research teams that used different games for promoting distinct learning outcomes report mixed results, some findings by the same researchers who used the same math video games were inconsistent (e.g., Ke, 2008a, 2008b, 2008c; Ke & Grabowski, 2007).

A meta-analytic review that quantitatively integrates findings of math video-gaming studies can provide an understanding of the effectiveness of game-based learning for student mathematics achievement. Previous computer-assisted instruction (CAI) meta-analyses focused on a broad range of interactive technologies, including drill-and-practice programs, web-based learning materials, simulations, virtual reality technologies, digital visualization tools, and video games (e.g., Bayraktar, 2001; Chambers, 2002; Christmann & Badgett, 2003; Cohen & Decanay, 1992). More recent media comparisons meta-analyses refine and focus on video games, but due to the paucity of video gaming research, video games are lumped together with simulations and virtual reality technologies (e.g., Merchant, Goetz, Cifuentes, Keeney-Kennicutt, & Davis, 2014). Like older CAI reviews, these meta-analyses did

not set game-based learning apart from learning with other interactive technologies, such as simulations and virtual reality. Moreover, due to scarce empirical video gaming research these CAI meta-analyses examined general academic achievement or combined mathematics and science academic achievement, without explicitly focusing on mathematics education. As such, no findings about the learning effectiveness of video games in mathematics education were reported.

Several meta-analyses have attempted to quantitatively synthesize findings of empirical research on game-based learning and academic achievement (e.g., Connolly et al., 2012; Young et al., 2012). However, due to methodological challenges associated with the shortage of rigorous research in game-based learning, a qualitative synthesis of video gaming studies was implemented instead of the initially planned meta-analysis. In addition, recent media comparisons meta-analyses (e.g., Clark, Tanner-Smith, & Killingsworth, 2016; Merchant et al., 2014; Vogel, Greenwood-Ericksen, Cannon-Bowers, & Bowers, 2006) spanned multiple content areas without addressing the specific instructional needs and requirements of a single subject area (such as mathematics).

2. Definition of Learning Video Games

The term "game" refers to a learning video game. Garris et al. (2002) note that there is little consensus in the literature on how to define educational games. Some consider Caillois's (1961) definition as the most comprehensive analysis of games, characterizing a game as "an activity that is voluntary and enjoyable, separate from the real world, uncertain, unproductive in that the activity does not produce any goods of external value, and governed by rules" (p. 442).

In this meta-analysis, we distinguish between games and simulations, as simulations and games offer different learning affordances. Simulations model real systems by displaying a procedure or phenomenon (Alessi & Trollip, 2001) and do not necessarily include learning objectives, but do allow students to interact with the simulation and observe how variable manipulation affects the observed phenomenon. Games, on the other hand, are designed to motivate students and create game-like learning experiences. Games often encourage competition by setting clear objectives to score as many points as possible, move up in difficulty level, or win in general (Young et al., 2012). For this meta-analysis we use Shute and Ke (2012) definition of video games, which suggests that good games must have interactive problem solving, specific goals/rules, adaptive challenges, control, ongoing feedback, uncertainty that evokes suspense and player engagement, and sensory stimuli (a combination of graphics, sounds, and/or storyline used to excite the senses). These gaming characteristics are essential for creating an effective learning environment that enhances students' engagement and facilitates knowledge and skills acquisition.

To examine the learning effectiveness of mathematics video games that included game attributes suggested by Shute and Ke (2012), this meta-analysis focused on modern digital games – the latest generation of learning video games developed using advanced technologies and recent pedagogical approaches (Kebritchi, Hirumi, & Bai, 2010). Unlike the earlier generation of educational games created in 1980s and 1990s, modern learning video games offer more advanced graphics and interface design, telecommunication and networking capabilities, immersive 3D learning environments, visual and audio effects, multi-player options, and a learner-centered approach, all of which are believed to increase gameplay motivation.

3. Aims of the Meta-analysis

This meta-analysis examined the relationships between game-based learning for mathematics skills development and student mathematics achievement in PreK-12th grades. Specifically, we assessed the relative effectiveness of game-based interventions compared to a traditional, non-video game-based classroom instruction. Our work was motivated by previous meta-analyses that emphasized the importance of studying factors which can influence the relationships among mathematics game-based learning and academic achievement, including mathematics skills and knowledge promoted in a game, game design elements, and design of game-based interventions (Clark et al., 2016; de Boer, Donker, & van der Werf, 2014; Sitzmann, 2011).

de Boer et al. (2014)'s meta-analysis revealed that instructional intervention methodology influenced students' academic performance. For instance, factors such as cooperative/individual learning and implementer of instructional interventions moderated the intervention effect. This area of research is certainly relevant and important for mathematics video game research, as the implementation of game-based interventions can directly affect students' mathematics achievement and engagement.

We conducted an extensive search of published and unpublished research on mathematics video gaming (described in detail later) in order to collect studies that compared the effectiveness of video gaming in mathematics with a traditional, non-video game-based classroom approach. Our initial list of study characteristics included:

- study participant characteristics (age, gender, race, learning disabilities, and socio-economic status)

- general study characteristics (length of game-based intervention, implementer of game-based intervention, teacher training on game-based instruction, teacher's familiarity with the learning game(s), amount of time students spent interacting with the game(s) before and after the video game intervention)
- game characteristics
- mathematics instructional approaches (lecture-based, inquiry-based, drill and practice)
- mathematics skills and knowledge promoted in the game
- publication characteristics (location of study, publication year and type)
- research characteristics (assessment type, outcome format, number of test items, instrument reliability)

However, this list of moderator variables was eventually reduced to six: grade level, instrument type, length of game-based intervention, country, publication year and type. The main reason for this reduction was due to methodological challenges and partially reported study characteristics and study methods. Specifically, classifying video games and math instructional approaches with regard to their characteristics and types presented considerable challenges for several reasons. First, many studies reported longitudinal research interventions that took place over an academic quarter or semester (e.g., Carr, 2012; Din & Caleo, 2000; Swearingen, 2011; Weiss et al., 2010). These studies employed multiple video games for teaching mathematics and likely used various mathematics classroom instructional approaches. In addition, studies often failed to describe the type of mathematics classroom instruction used for the so-called "traditional mathematics classroom instruction." We also considered classifying video

games as general-purpose commercial games and serious games that are “designed with the intention of improving some specific aspect of learning” (Derryberry, 2010). However, a vast majority of video games employed in the selected studies were serious games designed to improve specific math skills. Only three studies used general-purpose commercial games (*Brain Age 2* in Gelman, 2010; *My Sims* in Hawkins, 2008; *Sims 2* in Panoutsopoulos & Sampson, 2012). As such, for a quantitative comparison perspective this study characteristic was excluded. Furthermore, we attempted to code the studies with regard to math content (e.g., geometry, arithmetic, algebra). However, due to considerably different school settings and paucity of experimental and quasi-experimental research on math game-based learning, we were unable to classify math content.

In particular, the present study addressed the following research questions:

RQ1: What is the overall relative learning effectiveness of game-based interventions as compared to a traditional, non-video game-based classroom instruction for student mathematics achievement in PreK-12th grades?

RQ2: How heterogeneous are results from studies on the overall relative learning effectiveness of game-based interventions as compared to a traditional, non-video game-based classroom instruction for student mathematics achievement in PreK-12th grades?

RQ3: To what extent do study characteristics, namely grade level, instrument type, length of game-based intervention, country, publication year and type, moderate the effect?

4. Method

4.1 Literature search

Searches of ERIC, PsycINFO, Wilson, Google Scholar, JSTOR, and ISI Web of Science databases were performed to collect empirical studies, peer-reviewed journals, book chapters, thesis and dissertations, and conference papers, focusing on the effects of computer games on student mathematics achievement. The following keywords were used: *computer games, electronic games, video games, computer software, mathematics achievement, mathematics education, number sense, numerical skills, numbers, experiment, and experimental studies*. The initial search located 860 studies.

4.2 Inclusion criteria

All studies from the initial search were examined by two reviewers and assessed for inclusion in the meta-analysis using the following criteria:

1. Publication year range from 2000-2017
2. Study employed game-based and traditional, non-video game-based classroom instructional interventions
3. Study used at least one gamed-based classroom and one traditional classroom
4. Study participants were PreK-12th grade students
5. Student mathematics achievement was used as an outcome
6. It was possible to infer that the video games could be characterized as “good video games” (Shute & Ke, 2012)
7. Study reported sufficient data to calculate effect sizes

For the mathematics achievement outcomes requirement, eligible studies were required to measure students' mathematics performance. Studies focusing on related or general learning outcomes and benefits (e.g., creativity, cognitive strategies, self-efficacy, work ethics, enjoyment, motivation) were excluded. Upon review of the initial set of 860 studies there were 48 studies that satisfied the first five inclusion criteria items. However, many studies did not include a clear description of the employed learning games. These studies were further examined by the first two authors to determine if they could be characterized as learning games and if they included Shute and Ke's (2012) attributes of good learning games. The first author's field of expertise is Educational Research Methods, Measurement and Statistics, and Instructional Design. The second author specializes in Instructional Design and Technology with a research focus on video games. The first step in determining whether the employed video games could be characterized as "good video games" was to search the Web, including video game websites and YouTube videos about the games. If the initial Web search was insufficient, we searched whether the games were mentioned in the literature with regard to the game description, development, and research uses.

Moreover, some studies did not report sufficient data to calculate effect sizes. A total of 24 studies satisfied the inclusion criteria and were included in the meta-analysis. From these 24 studies we extracted 39 statistically independent effect sizes. The reason for having more effect sizes than the number of studies is that, in nine studies there were multiple groups (i.e., pairs) that produced more than one effect size. Unlike instances were, say, multiple outcomes are provided by the same sample of students (e.g., one reading outcome and one math outcome), these nine studies provided statistically independent effect sizes from multiple groups. Figure 1 provides a flowchart of the inclusion and exclusion decisions that lead to the final dataset.

Figure 1. Flowchart of inclusion and exclusion decisions.

4.3 Selection of variables

Part of our methods included moderator analyses of select study characteristics. The following moderator variables were categorized based on the common characteristics of the selected studies.

4.3.1 Grade level. Grade Level was a categorical factor consisting of three levels: Preschool-Kindergarten students (or its equivalent if outside of the United States), 1st-6th grade students, and 7th grade and above. This variable evaluated whether the effectiveness of mathematics game-based learning varied across different grade levels as to accommodate for a continued increase in difficulty of mathematics skills and decrease in student motivation to learn from preschool-elementary to middle-high school settings (Harter, 1981).

4.3.2 Instrument type. The instrument type variable classified the instrument types used in studies. This moderator consisted of three levels, the first of which was *researcher-made scale* (surveys, questionnaires, and tests created or partially created by researchers of the study). If researchers used selected questions or portions from a standardized instrument or large-scale assessment, this was also considered as a researcher-made instrument. The rationale for this is that once an instrument is altered from its original form, psychometric qualities often fluctuate and the instrument is no longer presented as intended by the original instrument creator(s).

The other two factor levels were commercial/standardized test and research-based scale. Commercial/standardized tests consisted of utilitarian standardized instruments and large-scale assessments. These instruments have long-standing validity, reliability, and psychometric properties which are generally accepted in research literature. Alternatively, research-based scales are instruments previously used by researchers and are generally accepted and used in studies in their respective field. Overall, the Instrument Type moderator variable was used in order to examine whether using different types of instruments (research-made,

commercial/standardized, and research-based scales) had an effect on student math achievement and showed significant differences among studies.

4.3.3 Length of game-based intervention. This moderator represented the duration of the game-based intervention in order to determine whether the intervention length contributed the effectiveness of game-based learning. Intervention length was categorized into three levels: up to one hour, between one hour and eight hours, and over eight hours.

4.3.4 Country. A dummy variable was created for the country moderator: Studies completed in the United States and studies completed outside of the United States. The United States and other countries have different educational systems. This moderator variable examined the effect of these differences on the study outcomes.

4.3.5 Publication year. We observed a somewhat large increase in the amount of video-gaming research over the last decade. Thus, the publication year moderator assessed differences among study results over time. We scaled publication year (i.e., first year of publication within the set of studies we set to zero, then next publication year to one, and so forth) for ease of interpretation.

4.3.6 Publication type. As is often in meta-analysis we assessed any differences of effects based on the publication type classification of a study. The publication type of a study consisted of two factor levels: journal and thesis/dissertation. Journal articles were considered published documents and theses and dissertations were considered unpublished documents.

4.4 Effect sizes and variances

The effect-size metric was the standardized mean difference. Some studies had relatively small sample sizes, thus we opted to use an unbiased version of the standardized mean difference proposed by Hedges (1981). The unbiased sample standardized mean difference for the k th of K studies is

$$d_k = \left(1 - \frac{3}{4(n_k^T + n_k^C - 2) - 1}\right) \frac{\bar{Y}_k^T - \bar{Y}_k^C}{S_k^P}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{Y}_k^T and \bar{Y}_k^C are respective mean mathematics achievement outcomes for the treatment and control groups, S_k^P is a pooled standard deviation, and n_k^T and n_k^C are respective treatment and control sample sizes. A positive effect size is interpreted as a mean difference favoring the treatment group and a negative effect size favoring the control group. In all instances the treatment group refers to the group of students who received a mathematics video-gaming intervention.

For five effect sizes, insufficient group-mean results were reported. In these cases we computed the standardized mean difference as

$$d_k = \pm \sqrt{\frac{F_k(n_k^T + n_k^C)}{n_k^T n_k^C}}, \quad (2)$$

where F_k is the F statistic from a one-way analysis of variance (see Borenstein, 2009). After computing effect-size estimates using (1) or (2), we calculated the sample variance of the estimate as

$$v_k = \frac{n_k^T + n_k^C}{n_k^T n_k^C} + \frac{d_k^2}{2(n_k^T + n_k^C)}, \quad (3)$$

where all terms have been previously defined.

4.5 Effect-size homogeneity

An important step when conducting a meta-analysis is determining the degree of homogeneity of a collection of effects. Several homogeneity measures were computed to assess the similarity of effects. First we computed the Q statistic (Hedges, 1982), a common index for assessing homogeneity in meta-analysis,

$$Q = \sum_{k=1}^K v_k^{-1} (d_k - \bar{d}_{FE})^2, \quad (4)$$

where \bar{d}_{FE} is the fixed-effect (i.e., inverse-variance weighted) mean. Under the null hypothesis of effect-size homogeneity, Q follows an approximate chi-square distribution with $K - 1$ degrees of freedom. Larger Q values correspond to more disagreement among effect sizes.

The second homogeneity measure was I^2 (Higgins & Thompson, 2002; Higgins, Thompson, Deeks, & Altman, 2003), computed as

$$I^2 = \frac{Q - K + 1}{Q} \times 100\%. \quad (5)$$

Rough interpretations of I^2 are *no variation*, *low variation*, *moderate variation*, and *high variation* for values 0, 25, 50, and 75, respectively (Higgins et al., 2003).

4.6 Unconditional random-effects model

Based on the results from homogeneity tests (shown in the Results section), as well as our intention to generalize results to more than the set of the collected studies, we adopted a random-effects model when making inferences to the overall results. A benefit of the random-effects model is the incorporation of a non-zero variance parameter, τ^2 , which represents a between-studies heterogeneity. This between-studies variance components represents the degree of heterogeneity among the study-specific effects (i.e., not at the primary-study level). Furthermore, under a random-effects model we allow individual study effects to differ across studies. The random effects model used in our research distributional form is

$$\begin{aligned}d_k &\sim N(\delta_k, v_k) \\ \delta_k &\sim N(\mu, \tau^2),\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

where δ_k represents the true value of the k th effect size, μ population parameter of the overall mean of effects, and τ^2 is the between-studies variance parameter (estimated using restricted maximum likelihood).

For the overall effect we computed a random-effects mean, its variance, and the associated 95% confidence interval. The random-effects mean estimate was calculated as

$$\bar{d}_{\text{RE}} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K d_k (v_k + \hat{t}^2)^{-1}}{\sum_{k=1}^K (v_k + \hat{t}^2)^{-1}}, \quad (7)$$

with an estimated variance

$$v_{\text{RE}} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^K (v_k + \hat{t}^2)^{-1}}. \quad (8)$$

4.7 Moderator analyses

As a follow-up to our unconditional overall models, we considered two types of conditional random-effects models to explain systematic effect-size heterogeneity: ANOVA-like models and meta-regression. Both modeling techniques use effect sizes as dependent variables and study characteristics as independent variables. In total, we examined six study characteristics (*Grade Level, Instrument Type, Length of Game-Based Intervention, Country, Publication Year and Type*) as moderators of effect sizes. Of the six coded variables, five were categorical (analyzed using ANOVA-like models) and one was continuous (analyzed using meta-regression).

For the ANOVA-like models, we report within-group effect means and their standard errors, as well as 95% confidence intervals. We also report two forms of chi-square statistics, Q_b and Q_w . These two measures assess predictor-specific significance in terms of explaining systematic effect-size heterogeneity (Q_b) and within-group variability of effects (Q_w). Because Q_w is group-specific, each group within a moderator (i.e., factor level) will have an estimate, while Q_b will have a single value for each specific factor.

The meta-regression results include coefficients and their standard errors, as well as 95% confidence intervals. Similar to the ANOVA-like modeling, we also provide two chi-square statistics, Q_m and Q_e . Both are related measures of a model fit, with larger values of Q_m and smaller values of Q_e corresponding to greater explanatory power of the effect-size heterogeneity by the set of model predictors.

4.8 Publication bias

Publication bias concerns studies with statistically significant and/or larger effects having publication preference over smaller and/or non-statistically significant effects (see Rothstein, Sutton, & Borenstein, 2006). We used several methods to check for publication bias. First, we provided a funnel plot (Figure 3) and assessed the expected relationship between effect-size magnitudes and their standard errors. Along with this graphic, we used three quantitative assessment methods: Trim and Fill (Duval & Tweedie, 2000), Egger's regression test (Egger et al., 1997), and Failsafe- N (Rosenthal, 1979). None of these tools prove the presence or absence of publication bias, rather they collectively indicate the likelihood of publication bias. All analyses and graphics were completed in R (R Core Team, 2016) using the *meta* package (Schwarzer, 2015) and *metaphor* package (Viechtbauer 2010).

5. Results

The 39 effect sizes in the meta-analysis ranged from -0.73 to 0.87, with roughly 67% of point estimates being positive (i.e., favorability to the video-gaming instruction group). Of the 24 unique studies, 9 contributed multiple (but statistically independent) effect sizes. Primary study sample sizes ranged from 41 to 437 students (combined intervention and control group samples) with

publication dates from 2008 to 2016. Based on point estimates and confidence intervals shown in Figure 2, the variability of effect-size magnitudes and precision appear somewhat heterogeneous. Not only do the effect-size magnitudes vary, the range spanned both positive and negative sides of the spectrum, further suggesting a diverse collection of effects. Both statistical assessments of homogeneity, $Q(38) = 92.25, p < .001$ and $I^2 = 60.19\%$, supported parts of our interpretations of Figure 2 regarding the effect-size heterogeneity. Given these results and our generalizability intentions when answering our research questions, we forwent using a more restrictive fixed-effect model and adopted random-effects models when making statistical inferences. Overall and moderator results are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. Forest plot for effect sizes. CI = Confidence Interval.

The overall random-effects weighted effect size was $\bar{d}_{RE} = 0.13, p = .02$, with an associated 95% confidence interval of [0.02, 0.24]. The overall effect of video-gaming instruction on mathematical achievement was marginally significant and quite variable, as denoted by the rather wide confidence interval and relatively large standard error ($SE = 0.06$). Furthermore, Figure 2 suggests that effects likely vary from study-to-study. This is supported by the between-studies variability estimate of $\hat{\tau}^2 = 0.07 (SE = .03)$.

When assessing publication bias, all indicators lead to a small likelihood of publication bias. The funnel plot (Figure 3) shows a moderate amount of effect-size symmetry. Trim-and-Fill results required no imputed effects to achieve asymmetry, which also aligns with the lack of statistical significance of Egger's regression test ($-0.820, p = .41$). Last, the Failsafe- N assessment required 141 additional non-statistically significant effects to be added for our overall mean results for its observed significance level to a non-statistically significant level (i.e., $\alpha > .05$).

Figure 3. Funnel plot of effect sizes with 95% confidence interval.

5.1 Moderator analysis results

In this section we discuss results of moderator analyses. The selected study characteristics had varying degrees of an explanatory power of the effect-size variability. We discuss each of the six moderators separately.

5.1.1 Grade Level. The grade level moderator did not explain a statistically significant amount effect-size heterogeneity ($Q_b(2) = 4.00, p = .14$). However, variability within groups was statistically significant for two of the three groups. More specifically, effect sizes varied within the 1st Grade – 6th Grade group ($Q_w(25) = 52.84, p < .001$) and the 7th grade and above group ($Q_w(9) = 24.22, p < .01$). Effect-size variability was not statistically significant for the Preschool-Kindergarten group ($Q_w(2) = 6.00, p = .05$). This result, in terms of statistical significance is dependent on the choice of Type I error level (i.e., α). In our case we choose to be more conservative and not assume statistical significance rather than risk the inflation of a result (i.e., assume statistical significance).

5.1.2 Instrument type. A non-significant amount of the effect-size heterogeneity was explained by the instrument type moderator ($Q_b(2) = 3.01, p = .22$). Thus, the use of different measurement instruments for the assessment of mathematics achievement did not seem to impact the effect of the intervention. However, two of the three measure types did show significant within-group variability, specifically both commercial/standardized tests ($Q_w(9) = 28.10, p < .001$) and researcher-made scales ($Q_w(17) = 41.51, p < .001$). The effect-size variability was not statistically significant for the researcher-based scales ($Q_w(10) = 13.62, p = .19$).

5.1.3 Length of game-based intervention. Like the grade level, country, and instrument type moderators, the length of game-based intervention did not explain a statistically significant amount of effect-size heterogeneity ($Q_b(2) = 2.51, p = .28$). However, all three groups showed a within-group variability: up to one hour ($Q_w(10) = 25.04, p < .01$), between one hour and eight hours ($Q_w(20) = 41.05, p < .01$), and over eight hours ($Q_w(6) = 22.92, p < .001$).

5.1.4 Country. Similar to the grade level moderator, we did not find a significant amount of explained effect-size heterogeneity for the country moderator ($Q_b(1) = .29, p = .60$). Nevertheless, variability within groups was found to be statistically significant. For studies from the United States, the homogeneity test statistic was $Q_w(16) = 35.99, p < .01$ and for studies outside of the United States the homogeneity statistic was $Q_w(21) = 54.20, p < .001$.

5.1.5 Publication type. The publication type moderator was one of the few moderators found to have explained a significant effect-size heterogeneity ($Q_b(1) = 6.49, p = .01$). This indicates that effect sizes varied between the type of study (journal or thesis/dissertation). The mean effect of the journal group was $0.21(SE = 0.06)$, while the mean for the thesis/dissertation group was $-0.07(SE = 0.09)$, showing a disagreement in both magnitude and direction. Moreover, the variance within groups differed between the source types. While the variance of effects within the thesis/dissertation type was not statistically significant ($Q_w(8) = 11.14, p = .19$), the variance of effects within the journal type was significant ($Q_w(29) = 58.92, p < .001$).

5.1.6 Publication year. The publication year variable was scaled so that the year 2000 (i.e., the earliest year of collected studies) was set to 0, then 2001 set to 1, and so forth. Our analysis revealed that the publication year slightly influenced the amount of

the effect-size variability ($Q_m(1) = 4.46, p = .03$). The slope from this regression model was $0.01(SE = .01)$, indicating a small increase in effect-size magnitude (i.e., an increase in the effect of video-gaming instruction on mathematics achievement) as the publication year of a study increased. However, the publication year moderator did not explain all effect-size variability ($Q_e(37) = 79.88, p < .001$).

Table 1

Moderator Analysis Results

Moderator [Q_b]	K_j	Mean(SE)	95% CI	Q_{w_j}
Overall	39	0.13(0.06)	[0.02, 0.24]	
Grade Level [$Q_b(2) = 4.00, p = .14$]				
Preschool – Kindergarten	3	0.58(0.25)	[0.09, 1.06]	6.00
1st Grade – 6th Grade	26	0.13(0.07)	[0.00, 0.27]	52.84****
7th grade and Above	10	0.05(0.10)	[-0.14, 0.24]	24.22**
Country [$Q_b(1) = 0.29, p = .60$]				
United States	17	0.10(0.08)	[-0.06, 0.26]	35.99**
Other	22	0.16(0.08)	[0.00, 0.32]	54.20****
Instrument Type [$Q_b(2) = 3.01, p = .22$]				
Commercial/Standardized Test	10	0.03(0.10)	[-0.17, 0.23]	28.10****
Research-based Scale	11	0.29(0.11)	[0.07, 0.50]	13.62
Researcher-made Scale	18	0.11(0.08)	[-0.05, 0.27]	41.51****
Length of Game-Based Intervention [$Q_b(2) = 2.51, p = .28$]				
Up to one hour	11	-0.03(0.12)	[-0.27, 0.21]	25.04**
Between one hour and eight hours	21	0.19(0.08)	[0.05, 0.34]	41.05**
Over eight hours	7	0.12(0.13)	[-0.13, 0.37]	22.92****

	<i>K</i>	Coefficient(<i>SE</i>)	95% CI	<i>Q_e</i>
Publication Type [$Q_b(1) = 6.49, p = .01$]				
Journal	30	0.21(0.06)	[0.10, 0.33]	58.92***
Thesis or Dissertation	9	-0.07(0.09)	[-0.25, 0.11]	11.14
Publication Year [$Q_m(1) = 4.46, p = .03$]	39	0.01(0.01)	[0.00, 0.02]	79.88***

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

Note: Means within groups are weighted under the mixed-effects model; *j* indicates a specific group; Regression coefficient is standardized.

6. Discussion

The empirical research on video games in mathematics education remains limited (Connolly et al., 2012) and our present study has further confirmed the paucity of research in this area. Despite a considerably large number of the reviewed studies (over 800), only 24 studies that compared mathematics game-based learning with traditional instructional methods were included in the meta-analysis (see Table 2). To generalize beyond the collection of studies in this meta-analysis, two types of random-effects models were used. One random-effects model provided an unconditional representation of the overall effect of video-gaming instruction on mathematics achievement. The second set of random-effects models looked at potential explanatory factors of systematic effect-size variation.

6.1 Overall Effectiveness

Our first research question was what is the overall relative learning effectiveness of game-based interventions as compared to a traditional, non-video game-based classroom instruction for student mathematics achievement in PreK-12th grades? A small but

marginally significant overall effect ($\bar{d}_{RE} = 0.13, p = .02$) suggests that mathematics video games contribute to a higher degree of mathematics achievement compared to traditional instructional methods. Although previous meta-analyses did not focus specifically on mathematics achievement, our findings converge with previous media comparisons meta-analyses that revealed benefits of CAI relative to non-CAI conditions (Clark et al., 2016; Merchant et al., 2014; Vogel et al., 2006).

Table 2

Study Characteristics Included in Meta-Analysis

<i>Study</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Instrument Type</i>	<i>Game(s)</i>	<i>Length of Game-based Intervention</i>
Bai et al. (2012)	437	7 th -12 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>DimensionM</i>	long
Beserra et al. (2014)	271	1 st -6 th	Brazil, Chile, and Costa Rica	research-based scale	Researcher-developed game	medium
Carr (2012)	104	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	iPad math games	long
Chang et al. (2012)	92	1 st -6 th	Taiwan	commercial/standardized test	Researcher-developed game	medium
Chang et al. (2015)	306	1 st -6 th	USA	commercial/standardized test	Researcher-developed game	medium
Ferguson (2014)	222	7 th -12 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>Slope game</i>	medium
Garneli et al. (2016)	80	1 st -6 th	Greece	commercial/standardized test	<i>Gem-game</i>	short
Gelman (2010)	80	7 th -12 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>Brain Age 2</i> , Nintendo DS	long
Giannakos (2013)	87	7 th -12 th	Norway	research-based scale	<i>Gem-game</i>	medium
Hall (2015)	405	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	iPad multiplication games	medium

Hawkins (2008)	139	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>MySims</i> Wii, Nintendo Wii	medium
Hung et al. (2014)	69	1 st -6 th	China	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Brick Breaker</i> game	medium
Ke (2008)	358	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>ASTRA EAGLE</i> (a series of web-based computer games; academic content is based on the Pennsylvania System of School Assessment (PSSA) standards for mathematics)	medium
King (2011)	128	7 th -12 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>VmathLive</i> (academic content is based on the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) standards)	medium
Lin et al. (2013)	64	1 st -6 th	Taiwan	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Monopoly</i> game	short
Panoutsopoulos & Sampson (2012)	57	1 st -6 th	Greece	commercial/standardized test	<i>Sims 2–Open for Business</i>	medium
Pareto et al. (2012)	47	1 st -6 th	Sweden	researcher-made instrument	Researcher-developed <i>Teachable Agents</i> game	long
Ploger & Hecht (2009)	196	1 st -6 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>Chartworld</i>	medium
Sedig (2008)	59	1 st -6 th	Canada	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Super Tangrams</i> game	medium
Shin et al. (2012)	41	1 st -6 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>Skills Arena</i>	long
Starkey (2013)	168	7 th -12 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>Lure of the Labyrinth</i>	medium
Sung, Chang & Lee (2008)	60	PreK-K	Taiwan	commercial/standardized test	Researcher-developed game	short
Swearingen (2011)	280	7 th -12 th	USA	research-based scale	Researcher-developed massive multiplayer online game (MMOG)	long
Weiss et al. (2006)	116	1 st -6 th	Israel	research-based scale	<i>Goldilocks</i> series games	long

Related to this, our second research question asked how variable are results from studies in terms of learning effectiveness of game-based interventions as compared to a traditional, non-video game-based classroom instruction for student mathematics achievement? Based on our assessment of effect-size heterogeneity (Q , I^2 , and $\hat{\tau}^2$), evidence pointed to disagreement among study results. In other words, not all studies agreed on the effectiveness of video-gaming instruction compared to traditional instruction with respect to measures of mathematical achievement.

6.2 Effectiveness by Study Characteristics

To further explore potential reasons for this effect-size heterogeneity, our third research question asked to what extent did study characteristics (grade level, country, instrument type, length of game-based intervention, publication type and publication year) moderate the effect. Of the six moderators used in our study, only two (publication type and publication year) had significant explanatory power with respect to effect-size heterogeneity.

6.2.1 Grade Level

With regard to grade level, results suggest that mathematics video games were similarly beneficial for students from various grade levels. These findings converge with Vogel et al. (2006) meta-analysis that examined the effects of games and simulations on student general performance across various disciplines. Vogel et al. (2006) found that interactive games and simulations were more beneficial for cognitive gains than traditional teaching methods for all age groups. Our literature search revealed only three published studies contrasting game-based learning and traditional classroom instruction in preschool-kindergarten students. Thus, the findings should be interpreted with caution when generalizing to the PreK-K

population since the results were obtained for the most part from studies with 1st-12th grade students.

6.2.2 Length of Game-Based Intervention

Studies used in the meta-analysis varied considerably in terms of the length of the game-based interventions (a single game session of 33 minutes as the shortest and multiple game sessions with a total of 10080 minutes as the longest). In line with previous research (Clark et al., 2016; Merchant et al., 2014), the length of game-based interventions did not have significant explanatory power. This finding may appear counterintuitive – one might expect that longer interventions should be more effective than shorter interventions. However, prior research on the effects of interventions in mathematics classrooms reports that intervention duration has only a small impact on students' academic achievement in both primary and secondary schools (Dignath & Büttner, 2008).

6.2.3 Instrument Type

Similar to Clark et al. (2016) and Merchant et al. (2014), this meta-analysis revealed non-significant differences among the studies that utilized researcher-made scales, commercial/standardized tests, or research-based scales. Although previously validated instruments such as commercial/standardized tests and research-based scales are usually associated with higher quality, some video-gaming studies assess learning outcomes for which validated instruments were unavailable. We note that if a study utilized only selected questions or portions from standardized instruments or large-scale assessments, this was considered as a researcher-made instrument in the present meta-analysis. Given that the present and previous meta-analyses found no relationship among different types of assessment instruments and academic achievement, we believe that utilizing researcher-made scales when pre-existing

validated instruments are unavailable would not necessarily diminish the quality of video game research.

6.2.4 Publication Year

The publication year of a study had significant explanatory power with respect to effect-size heterogeneity. Though only to a small degree, the effect of game-based learning on mathematics achievement increased as the year of publication increased. There are several possible explanations for this finding. First, because game-based learning is a developing area of research, it is plausible to assume that game-based interventions utilized in more recent studies were informed by previous video gaming research and therefore capitalized on past results. Furthermore, the video games industry is constantly seeking new ways to produce more engaging and higher quality games. These innovations could possibly contribute to higher mathematics achievement as well.

6.2.5 Publication Type

In addition to publication year, the publication type moderator demonstrated that the effect of video-gaming instruction on mathematics achievement differed between published and unpublished studies. The set of published studies had a statistically significant mean effect size which was positive and small-to-moderately large in magnitude. Conversely, the collection of unpublished studies had a mean effect size which was not statistically different from zero. This implies that published studies tended to claim larger effectiveness of the video-gaming intervention than their unpublished studies counterparts.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

This meta-analysis highlighted the need for more empirical research on mathematics video games in order to deepen our understanding of how video games can enhance mathematics

learning. Our initial intention was to examine various factors that could affect the relationship among mathematics game-based learning and academic achievement, including student individual differences, video game design characteristics, and attributes of video game-based interventions. However, most of the identified mathematics video game studies only provided partial information about the video games and game-based instructional interventions, thus limiting our ability to systematically examine the effects of several moderator variables. To advance research on mathematics game-based learning, we urge authors to include more detailed descriptions of research procedures and assessment instruments, as well as information about learning game(s) and expected learning outcomes. For example, it is important to report how the employed game(s) align with the classroom curriculum, the amount of video game training that teachers received, teacher familiarity with the game(s), how the video game intervention was implemented and who implemented it, the duration and frequency of video game interventions, and specific skills and knowledge promoted in the game.

With regard to future meta-analysis research on mathematics video games, there is a need to examine how video games facilitate acquisition of mathematics skills and concepts within different mathematical domains (e.g., geometry, arithmetic, algebra). Examining how video games facilitate acquisition of various skills can advance our understanding of how to select an optimal video game for enhanced learning of specific mathematics concepts and skills. Thus, future research should attempt to examine whether mathematics learning tasks can explain the relationships between video gaming and student achievement.

Clark et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of studying the relationships among game design and learning outcomes. This is certainly true for mathematics video game research. We should devote more attention to connecting game design characteristics with specific learning

outcomes across various mathematical domains. However, current literature reviews suggest that this type of research investigation can be a challenging task. Earlier research on educational video games usually employed a single video game for an instructional intervention, which allowed for a focus on game design and its impact on learning and engagement. However, technological advances in digital video games created new opportunities and expectations for teaching and learning. More recent studies implemented mathematics game-based learning using a series of video games or multiple video-gaming apps that utilized various game designs and genres and were played in the same game sessions, thus making the task of examining the role of game design quite difficult, if not impossible.

Last, studying the impact of game-based intervention attributes on student achievement can improve the quality of video game research in general and mathematics video gaming in particular (de Boer et al., 2014). This area of research is limited within the game-based learning literature. Identifying specific attributes of game-based interventions and examining relationships among these attributes and learning outcomes would be an important contribution to the literature on video games.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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Table 1

Moderator Analysis Results

Moderator [Q_b]	K_j	Mean(SE)	95% CI	Q_{w_j}
Overall	39	0.13(0.06)	[0.02, 0.24]	
Grade Level [$Q_b(2) = 4.00, p = .14$]				
Preschool – Kindergarten	3	0.58(0.25)	[0.09, 1.06]	6.00
1st Grade – 6th Grade	26	0.13(0.07)	[0.00, 0.27]	52.84****
7th grade and Above	10	0.05(0.10)	[-0.14, 0.24]	24.22**
Country [$Q_b(1) = 0.29, p = .60$]				
United States	17	0.10(0.08)	[-0.06, 0.26]	35.99**
Other	22	0.16(0.08)	[0.00, 0.32]	54.20****
Instrument Type [$Q_b(2) = 3.01, p = .22$]				
Commercial/Standardized Test	10	0.03(0.10)	[-0.17, 0.23]	28.10****
Research-based Scale	11	0.29(0.11)	[0.07, 0.50]	13.62
Researcher-made Scale	18	0.11(0.08)	[-0.05, 0.27]	41.51****
Length of Game-Based Intervention [$Q_b(2) = 2.51, p = .28$]				
Up to one hour	11	-0.03(0.12)	[-0.27, 0.21]	25.04**
Between one hour and eight hours	21	0.19(0.08)	[0.05, 0.34]	41.05**
Over eight hours	7	0.12(0.13)	[-0.13, 0.37]	22.92****
Publication Type [$Q_b(1) = 6.49, p = .01$]				
Journal	30	0.21(0.06)	[0.10, 0.33]	58.92****
Thesis or Dissertation	9	-0.07(0.09)	[-0.25, 0.11]	11.14
	K	Coefficient(SE)	95% CI	Q_e
Publication Year [$Q_m(1) = 4.46, p = .03$]	39	0.01(0.01)	[0.00, 0.02]	79.88****

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Giannakos (2013)	87	7 th -12 th	Norway	research-based scale	<i>Gem</i> -game	medium

Hall (2015)	405	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	iPad multiplication games	medium
Hawkins (2008)	139	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>MySims</i> Wii, Nintendo Wii	medium
Hung et al. (2014)	69	1 st -6 th	China	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Brick Breaker</i> game	medium
Ke (2008)	358	1 st -6 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>ASTRA EAGLE</i> (a series of web-based computer games; academic content is based on the Pennsylvania System of School Assessment (PSSA) standards for mathematics)	medium
King (2011)	128	7 th -12 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>VmathLive</i> (academic content is based on the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) standards)	medium
Lin et al. (2013)	64	1 st -6 th	Taiwan	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Monopoly</i> game	short
Panoutsopoulos & Sampson (2012)	57	1 st -6 th	Greece	commercial/standardized test	<i>Sims 2–Open for Business</i>	medium
Pareto et al. (2012)	47	1 st -6 th	Sweden	researcher-made instrument	Researcher-developed <i>Teachable Agents</i> game	long
Ploger & Hecht (2009)	196	1 st -6 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>Chartworld</i>	medium
Sedig (2008)	59	1 st -6 th	Canada	research-based scale	Researcher-developed <i>Super Tangrams</i> game	medium
Shin et al. (2012)	41	1 st -6 th	USA	research-based scale	<i>Skills Arena</i>	long
Starkey (2013)	168	7 th -12 th	USA	researcher-made instrument	<i>Lure of the Labyrinth</i>	medium
Sung, Chang & Lee (2008)	60	PreK-K	Taiwan	commercial/standardized test	Researcher-developed game	short

Swearingen (2011)	280	7 th -12 th	USA	research-based scale	Researcher-developed massive multiplayer online game (MMOG)	long
Weiss et al. (2006)	116	1 st -6 th	Israel	research-based scale	<i>Goldilocks</i> series games	long

Figures:

Figure 1. Flowchart of inclusion and exclusion decisions.

Figure 2. Forest plot for effect sizes. CI = Confidence Interval.

Figure 3. Funnel plot of effect sizes with 95% confidence interval.